

Lesson re-design for inclusive student-centred curricula

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6.1 Visible and action-based process

Redesigning lessons for inclusive student-centred pedagogies requires a fundamental shift in how educators conceptualize teaching and learning. Rather than focusing solely on content delivery or formal learning outcomes, inclusive lesson design places equal importance on the processes through which all students access, engage with, and make meaning from learning. This approach emphasizes flexibility, responsiveness, and co-construction of knowledge, ensuring that the diverse needs, backgrounds, and voices of students are acknowledged and embedded in the curriculum. Despite widespread claims of adopting student-centred approaches, faculty often default to traditional designs that prioritize transfer of disciplinary content knowledge and employability metrics over inclusive, participatory learning (Evans et al., 2017; Robinson, 2012; Brown, Wilson, & Slade, 2020). This chapter explores how intentional lesson re-design can align stated pedagogical commitments with inclusive, student-centred practices in ways that foster equity, engagement, and shared ownership of the curriculum.

According to Katsampoxaki-Hodgetts (2022), aligning all components of a lesson plan—such as content delivery modes, student engagement, assessment, and resources—with inclusive student-centred pedagogies can play a crucial role in making these processes more visible and action-based. This alignment activity itself can also serve as a beneficial process for faculty development. In this chapter, we will explore the steps faculty members can take to develop such lessons, focusing on the alignment of content delivery, student engagement, resources, and formative assessment with inclusive pedagogical practices. This approach is informed by a thematic analysis of reflective reports from six faculty members who applied these principles in their teaching and shared their experiences following peer observation (see Chapter 5), along with a discourse analysis of four lesson designs during the COALITION project. This analysis is further supported by quotes from the respective faculty members in follow-up semi-structured interviews.

6.2 Relevance of the topic

Student agentic engagement, where students actively participate in shaping their learning, has been advocated as a primary aim of higher education by educational scholars (Schuetz, 2008; Zepke et al., 2010), but it is rarely included as a distinct element in lesson design. Encouraging faculty to create lesson-specific, student-centred instructional activities that include action-based components and foster student agentic engagement has been shown to actively contribute to a supportive learning environment (Reeve & Shin, 2019). The alignment of lesson plan components with inclusive student-centred pedagogies involves incorporating engagement data into lesson plans (Banta et al., 2009) and combining design with self-reflection and self-regulation. Although descriptions of expected student conduct and ownership are uncommon (Eberly et al., 2001), emphasizing student agency as a key inclusive component can better demonstrate how students are engaged, as agency is something they do rather than possess (Biesta & Tedder, 2007). Moreover, rather than relying on knowledge transmission only, faculty reflections on their lesson plans can be further enriched by student feedback and engagement opportunities (Cook-Sather & Felten, 2017).

While faculty are not typically required to detail how students will be engaged during lessons, Biggs and Collis' (1982) taxonomy of learning outcome provides a constructive framework for students' cognitive development which can broaden the scope of lesson plans from merely discipline-specific content knowledge to fostering of student agency, skills, and literacies through scaffolding of the learning (Vygotsky, 1978). The alignment between student actions, learning outcomes, assessment, and the overall teaching and learning process is often not evident

(Biggs, 2014; Roseler et al., 2018). Yet, Katsampoxaki-Hodgetts (2022) used this alignment as a driver for educational development and demonstrated its reflective and developmental potential. In this context, Bloom's taxonomy (Krathwohl, 2002) helps clarify measurable outcomes using action verbs that aim to align instructional practices or specific learning interventions, maximising their effectiveness in driving change (Garfolo & L'Huillier, 2015). Additionally, inclusive student-centred lesson plans were preceded by peer observations with rubrics that delineate key components of inclusive student-centred pedagogies (see Chapter 2 and 5) and were accompanied by reflective reports designed to make inclusive student-centred components in the lesson plan visible to the participating faculty members. Also, the lesson plans were developed specifically to be implemented as part of an action research initiative (See Chapter 7) that followed the lesson plan design.

6.3 Practical issues of developing inclusive student-centred lesson plans

To gain deeper insights into faculty's values and goals, and how these manifest in lesson design, discourse analysis was conducted to compare the lesson plans of two science and two humanities faculty members who participated in the COALITION project (2023). Discourse analysis, an established qualitative method, allows researchers to examine overt or covert layers of dominance, control, and power as manifested in language (Rogers, 2004). This aligns with Habermas' (1976) view of language as ideological, and Fairclough's (1989) understanding of critical analysis as essential for revealing the interconnectedness of ideas and other discourses (intertextuality; cf. Lemke, 1992). In line with this, Wodak and Ludwig (1999) assert that language 'manifests social processes and interactions,' while Kress and van Leeuwen (1990) value different modes of representation when analysing educational texts. Overall, discourse analysis focuses on teacher language, context, power dynamics, and intertextuality, for example, as expressed in lesson plans.

Several key themes emerged regarding approaches to inclusivity, engagement, and learning outcomes. Both the science and humanities faculty members emphasised the need for inclusivity in content delivery. In fact, both recognize the importance of presenting content in multiple formats to cater to different learning styles as an inclusive practice. Professor 1 (science) incorporates 'diagrams, flowcharts, and infographics,' while Professor 2 uses 'videos and animations.' Humanities faculty also adopt multimodal approaches; Professor 3 includes 'multimedia presentations' and 'accessible documents,' while Professor 4 uses interactive tools like 'cloud surveys and role-play' to engage students.

Also, Professor 1 (science) highlights the importance of using 'plain language,' ensuring that content is 'accessible' and fostering an 'open, friendly academic environment.' Similarly, Professor 3 (humanities) focuses on using 'inclusive language' that avoids assumptions about gender or other identities and emphasizes 'diverse examples and references' to ensure that all students feel represented. Interestingly, during the interview, Professor 1 highlighted the need to design lessons with an emphasis on skills, not just content:

I believe that student skills should go beyond knowing Krebs cycle [red. series of biochemical reactions] or any such disciplinary content. Knowledge-based resources can now be accessed easily anywhere. Students need to learn how to study, how to select key information in order to understand, to learn how to cooperate, to collaborate as team members, to express their opinions and views, and justify them using evidence, to think critically. (Professor 1)

Professor 2 (science) introduces inclusivity through the use of 'visuals, multimedia resources, quizzes, and real-life examples,' while Professor 4 (humanities) suggests peer assessment and group work to enhance student involvement in content delivery. Both fields acknowledge the importance of making content accessible and relevant to all students, but the science faculty seem to focus more on technological and linguistic adjustments, whereas the humanities faculty seem to emphasize social and cultural representation. In the interview, Professor 4 stated:

This way you give students a really active role and you do not have to try and make groups homogeneous because student diversity can bring more benefits than you think. You make them learn from each other and at the end everyone has benefited somehow as a community of inquiry, cooperation, trust, common goals, and interests. This can be of benefit for teachers too. (Professor 4)

The teacher's language reflects strong engagement with the discourse of inclusive pedagogy. Terms like 'scaffolded approach,' 'inclusive lessons,' 'reflective practice,' and 'student engagement' are frequently used, signalling a deep familiarity with educational jargon that aligns with contemporary pedagogical theories. The frequent use of these terms suggests an internalisation of these concepts, which are presented as both essential and beneficial. For instance, the use of the 'scaffolded approach' implies a methodical approach to supporting student learning, drawing from Vygotsky's theories of cognitive development. Additionally, metaphors such as 'building bridges' (Professor 4) are used to describe the process of connecting with diverse students, reflecting a conceptualisation of education as constructing connections rather than merely transferring knowledge. This metaphorical language suggests a view of university teaching that emphasizes relationships and adaptability over rigid structures.

The teacher language reveals a complex negotiation of power within the educational university system. On the one hand, both science and humanities faculty position themselves as authorities in their lecture halls and seminar rooms, with significant control over lesson design and pedagogical approaches. For example, two faculty members discuss how they adjust their methods based on their observations and reflections, indicating a sense of autonomy (Professors 2 and 4). However, this authority is mitigated by a discourse of collaboration and mutual benefit, particularly in the context of inviting students to co-design inclusive learning environments.

All four faculty describe peer observation as a reciprocal process, where both the observer and the observed benefit from inspiring inclusive lesson design. This challenges traditional hierarchical structures in university education, where observation might be seen as a form of surveillance, evaluation, or compliance with top-down pressures. They perceive peer observation as a prerequisite to lesson design and frame it as a collaborative and reflective practice that empowers faculty to improve their teaching. This discourse subtly shifts power from institutional authorities to the faculty themselves, who become active agents in their professional development. The following quote from a Humanities faculty member illustrates these points:

What helped me a lot, was that it made me realise how I can connect pedagogical theory with research, I teach inclusive education in my classes and I am always looking for alternative ways of teaching and learning. It was great that we discussed with colleagues and they shared their ideas and perspectives on how inclusive classes should be. What really helped me was that it inspired me to engage my students as researchers in my classes doing inquiry... because engaging them in a lecture is fine but then I was inspired by the peer observation form that I used... I got this really great idea of asking students to conduct empirical surveys with regards to our lesson outcomes. (Professor 4)

The broader socio-political context of Greek university education shapes the teacher's language significantly. The emphasis on inclusive pedagogy and reflective practice can be seen as a response to both local and global educational trends that prioritise equity and student-centred learning, while the references to inclusive practices, such as adapting lessons for students with different learning needs and using diverse teaching strategies, reflect broader European educational policies that promote inclusion and diversity in higher education.

Furthermore, the faculty's narratives about the challenges of implementing these practices, such as the difficulty of knowing students' backgrounds, highlight the practical limitations within their local university context. These challenges may be exacerbated by larger systemic issues, such as large cohort sizes and limited resources. The faculty narratives thus reflect both an aspiration to align with global educational ideals and a recognition of the local constraints that make this challenging within their universities.

Moreover, the teacher language is deeply intertextual, drawing on multiple discourses within the field of university education. References to pedagogical theories, such as multiple intelligences and multiliteracies (Professor 3 and 4), position faculty within a global discourse on inclusive university education. Additionally, Professors 1 and 2 often align with official educational policies that emphasize student engagement and reflective teaching.

There is also a connection to broader narratives in education about the role of technology in facilitating inclusive education. For instance, a humanities faculty member discusses the use of tools like Padlet to enhance student engagement and participation (Professor 3). This aligns with contemporary educational narratives that advocate for the integration of digital tools to support diverse learners. The intertextual connections between the teacher language and these broader educational narratives suggest that their perspectives are shaped by a wide array of influences, from local educational policies to global pedagogical trends and educational research.

When it comes to learning objectives, all interviewed faculty members employ Bloom's Taxonomy, yet their emphasis differs. Professor 1 (science) outlines objectives across all levels of learning objectives, from *Remembering* to *Creating*, and incorporates inclusive objectives such as encouraging students to 'explore how different cultures approach medicinal healing.' On the other hand, Professor 3 (humanities) integrates inclusive objectives such as 'collaboration, communication, and reflection,' which are intended to foster a deeper understanding of diverse perspectives. This difference may reflect distinct focuses of the disciplines: science faculty seem to structure objectives around the mastery of content and technical skills, while humanities faculty tend to incorporate broader social and reflective skills.

Both science and humanities faculty design activities to cater to diverse learning preferences. Professor 1 employs a 'flipped classroom approach' and encourages peer teaching to allow students to 'showcase their unique strengths.' Similarly, Professor 2 integrates group projects and case studies that leverage students' diverse perspectives. Humanities faculty seem to be placing greater emphasis on dialogue and critical thinking. Professor 3 uses activities like think-pair-share and Socratic discussion to engage students in critical analysis and reflection. And Professor 4 emphasizes collaborative activities, such as role-play and group presentations, which encourage students to express themselves and engage in problem-solving.

Engagement is a central concern for all faculty members. Professor 1 (science) ensures a 'balanced mix of individual, pair, and group work,' while Professor 2 incorporates class discussions and digital platforms like blogs to encourage expression. Humanities faculty, such as Professor 3, use structured reading and peer review activities to ensure that students are actively involved in their learning. And Professor 4 facilitates engagement through interactive group work and discussions, often focusing on real-world scenarios.

Accessibility of resources is also a shared priority. Professor 1 mentions the use of 'assistive technologies' and ensuring that online resources are 'compatible with screen readers.' Professor 2 similarly ensures that all digital content is compatible with screen readers and accessible through 'high-contrast colours and readable fonts.' Professor 3 (humanities) also emphasizes the provision of resources in diverse formats and ensuring that materials are 'accessible to students with different learning needs.' Likewise, Professor 4 adds a focus on peer assessment and group-based problem-solving activities, which not only make resources more accessible but also encourage students to actively engage with and contribute to the learning material.

Last but not least, both science and humanities faculty challenge the idea that fully inclusive design is possible, given the limitations of time, resources, and knowledge about students. Professors 1 and 3 argue that while inclusivity is an important goal, it is unrealistic to expect faculty to know every aspect of their students' backgrounds. Instead, they advocate for a more practical approach, where inclusivity is about providing a range of learning opportunities rather than tailoring activities to every individual.

6.4 Resources: illustrative insights for an inclusive lesson design

Thematic analysis of the faculty members' six reflective reports gave rise to valuable insights into the efficacy of aligning lesson design with inclusive student-centred pedagogies. Faculty reported several key takeaways including

increased awareness, enhanced teaching practices, but also described challenges. In fact, designing for inclusivity raised awareness of the diverse needs of students and the importance of accommodating these needs in all aspects of teaching (Professor 1, 2, and 3). In terms of enhanced teaching practices, faculty found that incorporating inclusive practices not only benefited students but also enriched their own teaching practices, making them more reflective and adaptable (Professor 3 and 4). Yet, although the process was beneficial, faculty identified challenges such as time constraints, resource limitations, and the need for additional training in inclusive practices (Professors 2, 3, and 4).

6.4.1 Identification of content

The first step in designing an inclusive lesson is to identify the content that will be taught. Faculty should ask themselves: What content do I want to teach and what changes will I make in order to make the learning assignments and environment more inclusive?

- *Diverse Perspectives:* Ensure the content includes diverse perspectives and examples that resonate with all students. For example, Professors 1, 2 and 3 emphasized the importance of using inclusive language and integrating diverse examples to foster a welcoming environment.
- *Multimodal Content Delivery:* Modify the content to be accessible through various formats, such as visual, auditory, and textual. Professor 3 mentioned the challenge of finding and incorporating diverse materials that are accessible to all students, highlighting the need for careful planning.

6.4.2 Identification of inclusive student-centred learning objectives

Once the content is identified, the next step is to determine the learning objectives. Faculty should consider questions such as: What do I expect each of my students to be able to do or know and are there learning objectives that I can add to foster inclusive pedagogies?

- *Diverse Cognitive Skills:* Use a taxonomy to create learning objectives that address both lower and higher-order cognitive skills. This approach ensures that all students, regardless of their starting point, can progress in their learning.
- *Inclusive Objectives:* Include objectives that promote inclusivity, such as developing skills in collaboration, communication, and critical thinking. Professor 2 suggested breaking down complex tasks and allowing students to demonstrate understanding in various ways, catering to neurodiversity and diversity of students' abilities.

6.4.3 Inclusive learning activities

The design of learning activities should reflect inclusivity, ensuring all students can participate and learn effectively. Faculty should reflect on the following design questions: What activities have I designed to facilitate learning for all students and how can I observe that student learning actually happened?

- *Varied Activities:* Design activities that cater to various learning preferences and profiles, such as group work, individual tasks, and interactive sessions. Professor 4 highlighted the importance of using technological tools like quizzes and polls to engage students' anonymous responses and project student learning during the process.
- *Formative Assessment:* Align assessment with learning outcomes by using formative assessments that provide feedback during the learning process. Professor 3 recommended incorporating self-assessment tasks, allowing students to reflect on their learning and identify areas for improvement.

6.4.4 Identification of engagement opportunities for all

Engagement is key to student success, and faculty should provide opportunities for all students to act and express themselves. They should consider questions such as: Have I provided opportunities for all students to act and express themselves and am I using various digital media and modes beneficial for student learning?

- *Digital Tools and Media*: Utilize digital tools and media to create a dynamic and inclusive learning environment. Professor 4 emphasized the use of educational technologies and media to engage students, particularly those who may not be physically present in the classroom.
- *Collaborative Learning*: Encourage collaboration through group work, peer review, and discussions. Professor 3 focused on the importance of group discussions and peer review tasks to foster a collaborative learning environment.

6.4.5 Provision of resources

Resources should be accessible and appropriate for all students. Faculty should reflect on the following questions when designing an inclusive lesson: Are resources accessible to all students and how can I ensure these resources and their content are appropriate for all students?

- *Accessible Materials*: Ensure that all resources, such as readings, videos, and online tools, are accessible to students with different needs. Professor 3 noted the challenges of creating or finding accessible versions of materials, underscoring the importance of this step.
- *Relevant yet diverse Resources*: Select resources that are relevant and reflect diverse perspectives, catering to the varied backgrounds and interests of students.

6.4.6 Multiple representation of input

Finally, faculty should evaluate whether they are the only source of input and consider how to present content in multiple ways to accommodate all student needs. They should reflect on questions such as: am I the only source of input and have I made any changes that allow all students to take agency over their learning?

- *Multimodal Representation*: Present content using various formats—lectures, videos, interactive tools—to cater to different learning preferences. All faculty members recognized the need to incorporate multiple representations of content, including digital and interactive methods.
- *Student-centred Learning*: Provide students with choices in how they engage with and demonstrate their learning. Professor 2 and 3 described experiences with interdisciplinary and multi-environment approaches and highlighted the benefits of allowing students to take ownership of their learning.

6.5 Conclusion

Curriculum redesign that embraces inclusive student-centred pedagogies is fundamental to transforming higher education into a space that equitably serves all learners. Moving beyond surface-level adjustments, the re-design process requires a systemic rethinking of how content, learning outcomes, instructional strategies, and assessments are aligned to meet diverse student needs. The experiences of the six COALITION university teachers illuminate the pedagogical depth and critical reflection involved in this endeavour. Their work demonstrates how revisiting and restructuring curricula can create more participatory, multimodal, and culturally responsive learning environments. While challenges such as institutional constraints and faculty readiness persist, the re-design of curriculum, when guided by inclusive principles, it enhances both student engagement and teacher agency. Ultimately, inclusive curriculum redesign is not just a teaching enhancement, but a strategic process for enacting social justice in education.

6.6 References

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